

Ganadharas of Mahāvira

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Soon after the attainment of *kaivalya* Mahāvira visited Pāva and held religious discourse in the garden of one Mahāsena. In the same garden a *Brahmana* named Somila had made arrangement for a *yagya* and invited learned *Brāhmanas*. Eleven of them came to Mahāvira with a desire to have religious discussion with him. They were influenced by the personality and spiritual attainments of Mahāvira so, much so, that they decided to join him as his disciples. Incidentally, the first disciples of Mahāvira turned to be his principal disciples known as *Ganadharas*. They became well-versed in the twelve *angas* and fourteen *pūrvas*. Details about them are:

Name	Caste	Gotra	Residence
1. Indrabhuti	<i>Brahmana</i>	<i>Gautama</i>	Gobbaragrama
2. Agnibhuti	<i>Brahmana</i>	<i>Gautama</i>	Gobbaragrama
3. Vāyubhuti	<i>Brahmana</i>	<i>Gautama</i>	Gobbaragrama
4. Vyakta	<i>Brahmana</i>	<i>Bhāradvaja</i>	Kottaga Sannivesa
5. Sudharman	<i>Brahmana</i>	<i>Agnivesyayana</i>	Kottaga Sannivesa
6. Mandila	<i>Brahmana</i>	<i>Vasista</i>	Mauriya Sannivesa
7. Moriyaputra	<i>Brahmana</i>	<i>Kāsyapa</i>	Mauriya Sannivesa
8. Akampita	<i>Brahmana</i>	<i>Gautam</i>	Mithila
9. Achalabhrāta	<i>Brahmana</i>	<i>Hāritayana</i>	Kosal
10. Metārya	<i>Brahmana</i>	<i>Kaundinya</i>	Tungiya Sannivesa
11. Prabhāsa	<i>Brahmana</i>	<i>Kaundinya</i>	Rājagriha

Though the *samgha* consisted of only nine *ganas* all these eleven chief disciples were called *ganadharas* because they had instructed *Sramanas* in great number. The *Kalpa Sūtra*¹

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mentions exact number of *Sramanas* instructed by each one of them, but we cannot be sure on this point. Except Indrabhuti and Sudharman, rest nine *ganadharas* died in the very life time of Mahāvira. Indrabhuti is said to have died twelve years after the *nirvana* of Mahāvira at the age of 92.

Though he was favourite of Mahāvira and survived him, it was Sudharman who became head of the Jain *Samgha* after Mahāvira². Sudharman died twenty years after the demise of Mahāvira. The *Kalpa Sūtra* states that all the *nirgrantha Sramanas* of the present time are descendants of Sudharman and rest of the *Ganadharas* left no descendants.³

Jain Samgha after Mahāvira

The sources which contain information about the successors of Mahāvira in the pontificate of the *Samgha* are *Kalpa Sūtra Theravali (Sthaviravali)*, *Nandi Sūtra* and *Avasyaka Sūtra*. The list of the pontiffs given in the *Nandi* and *Avasyaka Sūtras* is quite in agreement with the list given in the *Kalpa Sūtra* up to Mahāgiri and Suhastin who belonged to the eighth generation after Mahāvira. After it the succession list of the pontificates gets divided into two branches, one starting from Mahāgiri and the other starting from Suhastin. The list of patriarchs given in the *Nandi* and *Avasyaka Sūtras* is quite distinct from the one given in the *Kalpa Sūtra*. The list of the; *Kalpa Sūtra* begins from Suhastin and this was the most prominent line of succession as almost all the legends found in the *Parisistapārvan* of Hemachandra and other later Jain texts pertain to the lives of the patriarchs of this line. The names of first six successive leaders of the Jain *samgha* are: (i) Sudharman, (ii) Jambu, (iii) Prabhava, (iv) Svayarnbhava, (v) Yasobhadra, (vi) Bhadrabāhu and Sambhutavijai. Then after the burden of the leadership of the *samgha* fell on the shoulders of Sthulabhadra. It was during this period that the Council of Pataliputra was held and the *angas* took a definite shape. Sthulabhadra had two disciples, Mahāgiri and Suhastin. With Mahāgiri and Suhastin started two lines of succession. It appears that at this stage the unity of the *samgha* was shattered and finally the *samgha* was split into *Svetāmbara* and *Digambara* sects.

Schisms in the Jain Samgha

The evidence of the early Jain texts clearly indicates that the monastic life in Jain religion had started in quite early times. The *samgha* organised by twenty third tirthankara Pārsvanātha was very effective and remained functioning centuries after his demise. The twenty third chapter of the *Uttaradhyayana Sūtra* entitled "*Gautam-Kesi Samvāda*" clearly tells us that the monastic orders of Pārsvanātha and Mahāvira functioned simultaneously as separate

organisations for some time. The same text tells us that the unity between the two orders was forged as a compromise between Kesi Kumāra and Indrabhuti Gautama, the followers of Pārsvanātha and Mahāvira respectively.

It appears that the Jain *samgha* was clearly split into two sects, *Digambara* and *Svetāmbara*, after a few centuries of the demise of Mahāvira. This division proved to be of lasting effect and even today the Jain community is divided into these two major schools.

Even before the division of the Jain *samgha* into *Digambara* and *Svetāmbara* sects some minor schisms had already taken place in the Jain order. These splits-have been chistened as *Nihnava*s in the Jain texts. These *Nihnava*s are said to be seven in number.

First *Nihnava*

This *nihnava* is known as *bahurayavada* and was started by Jamali the son-in-law of Mahāvira. Jamali has been referred to in a number of Jain texts such as *Visesāvasyaka bhāsyā*, *Āvasyaka*, *Haribhadriya Tīkā*, *Sthānānga* commentary and *Uttarādhayayana* commentary by Nemichandra.

Jamali, a resident of Kshatriya Kunda, was initiated as a monk by Mahāvira. However, he developed doctrinal difference with Mahāvira and finally separated himself with his followers from the *samgha* and started the first *nihnava* fourteen years after Mahāvira obtained omniscience. The sect started by him could not last long and finally most of his followers rejoined the original *samgha*.

Second *Nihnava*

The second *nihnava* is known as *jīvapaesiya nihnava* and was started by *Tisyagupta* sixteen years after the attainment of *kaivalya* by Mahāvira. He disagreed with the tenet that *jīva* is the composition of all the parts of an animate being into one whole and instead held that the last part of the soul which completes its composition is *jīva*. The sect started by *Tisyagupta* also could not last long. Finally, his followers realised the falsity of his views and came back to the original *samgha*.

Third *Nihnava*

The third *nihnava* is known as *avattagaaddin*. This schism was started by *Asadhabhuti* at *Seyaviya* two hundred fourteen years after the death of Mahāvira. The adherents of this sect

believed that there is nothing *vyakta* in the world. Hence, they disregarded all the external observances. This is precisely the reason that this *nihnava* has been named *Avyakta nihnava*.

Fourth Nihnava

This split was started by Asvamisra two hundred twenty years after the death of Mahāvira. The followers of Asvamisra were known as *samuccheiyavadin*. They held that everything of the world is transient and is destroyed after its origination. So, the effects of good or bad deeds are immaterial.

Fifth Nihnava

This *nihnava* came into existence two hundred twenty-eight years after the death of Mahāvira and was started by *Ganga*, a disciple of Dhana Gupta. The followers of *Ganga* were called '*dokriyavadin*' They did not agree with the original Jain tenet that the experience of different actions cannot be had simultaneously. Instead, they held that opposite feelings, such as warmth and cold, can be experienced simultaneously.

Sixth Nihnava

This schism was started by Roha Gupta at a place named Antaranjia five hundred and forty-four years after the death of Mahāvira. The adherents of this school were called *nojvavadin* as well as *Terasiya (trairasika)*. They held that there is a third category of *dravya* called *Nojīva* in addition to *jīva* and *ajīva*.

Seventh Nihnava

The leader of this split was Gosthamahila It was started by him at Dasapur five hundred and eighty-four years after the death of Mahāvira. The followers of Gosthanmahila were called *Abadhiyavadin*. They believed that the soul is simply touched by the *karma-paramamis* and not bound by them.

It is to be noted that the *Nihnavas* discussed above were minor schisms and could not adversely affect the Jain monastic order. They could not last long and either became obsolete or got merged in the original *samgha*. The veracity of the accounts of these schisms as given in the Jain texts is very difficult to ascertain. Much of the details is fanciful. But the fact that there have been minor schisms in the Jain order can hardly be denied.

The split of Jain Samgha into Svetāmbara and Digambara Sects

The organisation of the Jain *samgha* remained almost unaffected by the minor schisms mentioned above. Their impact was very short lived. But the split of Jain *samgha* into the *Digambara* and *Svetāmbara* sects is a major event in the history of Jain religion. The Jain community was divided into two separate groups who, in course of time, developed their distinct organisation, literature and tradition of art. Even to-day they have maintained their distinct identities.

It is to be noted that both the sects do not have serious doctrinal differences. Their religio-philosophical beliefs and mythologies are identical. The only point of difference in mythological beliefs is that Mallinātha, the nineteenth *Tīrthamkara*, was a woman according to the *Svetāmbaras* whereas, according to the *Digambaras*, he was a man. The ideological basis of this difference of contention lies in the fact that according to the *Digambaras* a woman is not entitled to the enlightenment whereas the *Svetāmbaras* believe that a woman can obtain it. The main differences between them are related with ethical practices.

When and how the split of Jain *samgha* into *Swetmbara-Digambara* sects took place is a problem which is still not convincingly solved and the historians are not unanimous on the point. Even the *Svetāmbaras* and *Digambaras* give different account of this rift.

The *Digambara* version of the rift is recorded in the *Brihatkathā* composed by Harisena in 931 AD. It is stated here that Bhadrabāhu had predicted a terrible famine in the country of Magadha for a period of twelve years during the reign of Chandra Gupta Maurya. In order to save their lives from the famine a section of monks under the leadership of Bhadrabāhu migrated to the south India and the rest remained in the north India.

After sometimes the leaders of the order in north India met in Ujjayini. Still the calamity of famine was persisting and the leaders allowed the monks to wear a piece of cloth (*ardhaphālaka*) in order to avoid obscenity while touring for begging alms. These monks got accustomed to wearing *ardhaphālaka* and they refused to get rid of this practice even when the famine was over. The conservative elements in the order and particularly those who had returned from the south Indian migration highly resented to this development. It is further stated that these *ardhaphālaka* monks were once invited by Chandralekha queen of king Lokapala of Valabhipur. Seeing them neither clothed nor naked the king got annoyed where upon the queen asked the monks to wear full clothes. Thenceforth, the monks began wearing white clothes and came to be called *Svtapatas* or *Svetāmbaras*.

Thus, according to the *Digambaras* the Jain monks did not wear any clothes in the beginning but later on a section of them started wearing white clothes and got split from the original *samgha* (*mūla samgha*) and the split of *samgha* in the forms of *Digambara* and *Svetāmbara* was affected.

However, the *Svetāmbaras* give a different account of the split. According to them the *samgha* was divided six hundred nine years after Mahāvira's death by Sivabhuti. It is stated in the *Āvasyakabhāṣya*, a work of 5th century AD, that Sivabhuti, a resident of Rathavirapur, was an employee of the local king. He had successfully fought many battles on behalf of the king and had won laurels. Consequently, he turned to be very proud and used to come home very late in the night. On the complaint of his wife, one night his mother did not open the door and asked him to go elsewhere. Sivabhuti left the home and entered in a dwelling which was incidentally a Jain monastery (*upāśraya*). He requested the acharya (priest) of the monastery to initiate him but his request was turned down. Sivabhuti, then, plucked out his hairs himself and started wandering as a monk with others. After some time, he came to his native place. When the king was informed of his arrival, he sent a precious shawl (*ratna kambala*) to him as a gift. Possession of such a precious article by a monk was protested by his senior but Sivabhuti did not pay any heed to his advice. His senior, then tore off the shawl and used it as mattress. At that time Sivabhuti did not say anything but out of reaction gave up all clothing which ultimately resulted in the schism of the order.

In another version of Sivabhuti episode it is stated that Sivabhuti did not agree with his teacher Krisnarsi that the *jinakalpikas* (adherents of *jinakalpa*) are of two kinds. While some observe absolute non possession, others may have necessary requisites. Sivabhuti asserted that a follower of *jinakalpa* should strictly observe the principle of austerity including nudity. He gave up all clothing and created a schism. He was joined by Kaundinya and Kottavira as his disciples. His sister Uttara is also said to have joined him, but was forbidden by him from observing nudity. The members of this group were initially called *bodiyas* but because of their practice of nudity they were later on known as *Digambaras*.

Thus, according to the *Svetāmbara* tradition the *Digambara* sect originated 609 years after Mahāvira's death, that is, in the first century AD.

The accounts of the *Svetāmbara* and *Digambara* traditions are so discrepant that on the basis of them it is very difficult to reach a conclusion as to when and how the split occurred. Nonetheless, they give us certain clues which may help us in settling this issue.

Hoernle in his article on the *Ājivikas* in the Encyclopaedia of Religion and Ethics expressed the opinion that the Digambaras were originally *Ājivikas* who, after their annoyance with Gosāla, joined the order of Mahāvira as his disciple. Hoernle was led to derive this conclusion on the basis of the practice of *achelakatva* (nudity) of the *Ājivikas* and a statement of the commentator Silānka in his commentary on the *Sūtrakritariga* that the revilers of the followers of Mahāvira were the *Ājivikas* or *Digambaras*. Hoernle's contention is hardly convincing and A. K. Roy is quite correct when he states. "The bulk of the evidence however is against Hoernle's conjecture, and the theory that some *Ājivikas* formed the nucleus of the *Digambara* sect cannot be built upon this one stray reference by Silānka".⁴

A. K. Roy thinks that the process of split was gradual but it was completed at the end of 5th century A. D. when the Valabhi Council was held. He has cited some epigraphic and iconographic evidence in support of his contention.⁵ But his conclusion is based more on assumption than on evidence. Moreover, the assignment of such a late date for the split is not in consonance with what the facts of the traditions have to tell us.

It is quite evident from the early Jain texts that Mahāvira lived strict austere life and observed *achelakatva* (nudity) and preached the same to his disciples. His followers earnestly observed the ethical regulations for some time even after his death. Parallel to Mahāvira's. order the *samgha* established by Pārsvanātha was also functioning. The followers of Pārsvanātha did not observe the practice of nudity and used to wear clothes. After the death of Mahāvira, Indrabhuti Gautama was leading the *samgha* and Kesi Kumara was the leader of the *samgha* of ParSva Natha. The twenty third chapter of the *Uttarddhyayana Sūtra* entitled '*Gautama-Kesi Samvāda*' inform us that the two leaders incidentally met in Sravasti with their followers. It was generally realised by the monks that both the laws are pursuing the same end but why does the order of Pārsvanātha allow an under and upper garment and that of Mahāvira enjoin five vows and forbid wearing clothes? When this question was raised by Kesi, Gautama gave a convincing reply so far as the discrepancy in the number of vows is concerned and Kesi was fully satisfied. On the matter of nudity or wearing of clothes the reply of Gautama was : "Deciding the matter by their superior knowledge, the *tīrthamkaras* have fixed what is necessary for carrying out the law. The various outward marks (of religious men) have been introduced in order that people might recognise them as such; the reason for the characteristic marks is their usefulness for religious life and their distinguishing character. Now the opinion (of the *tīrthamkaras*) is that knowledge, faith and right conduct are the true causes of final liberation."⁶ After being fully satisfied Kesi with his followers accepted the law of the five

vows and both the *samghas* got united. It appears that the question of wearing clothes or not was left to the desires of monks. But the existence of two-fold *kalpa*, namely, *jinakalpa* and *sthavirakalpa*, in an organisation could not last long. As a result, in course of time, the *samgha* got split into two sects *Digambara* and *Svetāmbara*.

The lists of the names of the leaders of *samgha* after Mahāvira found in the *Kalpa Sūtra*, *Nandi Sūtra*, *Āvasyaka Sūtra* and *Parisiptapārvaṇ* indicate that the unity of the *samgha* was maintained up to the time of Sthulabhadra as both the traditions generally agree with the succession of pontificates up to Sthulabhadra. He had two disciples Mahāgiri and Suhastin and the lists of the names of successors of these two are given in the *Nandi Sūtra* and *Kalpa Sūtra* which are quite different. On the basis of it, it may be construed that the split in the *samgha* was affected soon after Sthulabhadra. The major events of the Jain monastic order are reckoned with reference to Mahāvira era which is supposed to have started from 527 B.C., the traditional date of the nirvana of Mahāvira. According to it the accession of Chandra Gupta Maurya to the throne and the death of Bhadrabahu took place in 155 and 170 years respectively after the death of Mahāvira. If these dates are converted into the Christian era, they will be 357 B. C. and 372 B. C. respectively. It is a point of general agreement among historians that Chandra Gupta's accession took place in and around 321 B. C. This date does not tally with the traditional calculations of the Jains. The possibility of miscalculation on the part of the Jains cannot be ruled out. Since the reign of Chandra Gupta ended in 297-298 B. C. and the contemporaneity of Chandra Gupta and Bhadrabāhu is attested by the Jain sources, it may be safely assumed that in the beginning of the third century B. C., Sthulabhadra took the charge of the leadership of the Jain *samgha*. Thus, there is a strong possibility that the schism occurred in the first half of the third century B. C.

This conjecture gets support from an account of the Jain texts. It is said that Sthulabhadra convened a council at Pataliputra during the period off a mine when Bhadrabāhu had gone to south India with a section of monks and he did not invite Bhadrabāhu to attend this council. It is quite strange that Bhadrabāhu who was the only person well-versed in all the *angas* and *pūrvas* was not invited and in his absence, the form of canonical literature was fixed in this council. Does this not bespeak of some sort of dissension in the Jain Order?

It appears that after the amalgamation of the orders of Pārsva and Mahāvira the discipline of nudity got loosened. The *Sthavirakalpa* became more popular among monks. However, more orthodox among them continued adhering to the *jina kalpa*. So long as the

number of monks was small, there was no difficulty in maintaining the *jina kalpa*. We know that the monks depend on society for their subsistence. With the increase of number of monks, the magnitude of their dependence on society might have increased. As such, movement of monks in big number in nude form for begging purposes might have caused a sense of shyness and hesitation. They will have been prompted to put on clothes without incurring any sacrilege particularly when *sthavirakalpa* was there. After all, wearing clothes or nudity are simply outer marks of religion and they are insignificant so far as the realisation of *moksha* is concerned.

This, is not to say that *Jina Kalpa* was replaced by the *sthavira kalpa*. The monks with strong orthodoxal attitude continued the practice of nudity. In their eyes complete detachment from worldly possession was essential for the realisation of the highest goal and possession or putting on clothes constituted the transgression of the canon of *aparigraha*. The number of such monks was not very small and they formed a group in the general community of the monks. With the passage of time their attitude got more and more stiffened and they disagreed on more points with the rest others. They denied the womanhood of Malli Natha, the nineteenth Tirthankara of the Jain tradition, only on the ground that *Jinahood* can't be obtained without practising nudity and a woman cannot do it. They also deny the efficacy of womenfolk in obtaining salvation. Their orthodoxal attitude is reflected in their denial of Mahāvira's marriage. In this context we can understand as to why they do not accept the authenticity of canonical texts compiled in the councils of Pataliputra and Valabhi.

It is to be noted here that the split of the order did not occur all of a sudden. The process of division was gradual. It seems to have started in the first half of third cent. B. C, as has been pointed earlier, and was completed in the first coming A.D. If some minor details of the *Svetāmbaras* account are overlooked there is no reason to doubt the authenticity of the account that the *Samgha* was split into the *Digambara* and *Svetāmbara* sects 609 years after the death of Mahāvira, that is first cent A. D. The tradition cannot be rejected lock, stock and barrel.

Main Points of difference between *Svetāmbara* and *Digambara* traditions

1. While *Svetāmbaras* used to wear white garments, the *Digambaras* practised nudity.
2. The *Svetāmbaras* believed that Mahāvira was married with Yasoda and had a daughter from her, the *Digambaras* altogether deny it.
3. According to the *Svetāmbaras* 19th Tirthankara Mallinātha was a woman, but the *Digambaras* believe that Mallinātha was a man.

4. The *Svetāmbaras* believe that a woman can obtain moksha but according to the *Digambaras* they are not entitled to it.

5. According to the *Svetāmbaras* the embryo of Mahāvira was transferred from the womb of *Kshatram* Trisala to that of *Brahman* Devananda. The embryo transfer story is not accepted by the *Digambaras*.

6. The *Svetāmbaras* believe in the authenticity of the existing twelve *angas*. The *Digambaras* believe that the original twelve *angas* are extinct.

7. The *Svetāmbaras* adorn the images of Tirthankaras with clothes and ornaments. The *Digambaras* are opposed to such clothing or ornamentation.

In addition to these major differences, they developed differences on some minor points as well. They are trivial and have little historical significance. In fact, there were no significant doctrinal differences. Almost all the cardinal principles of Jainism are accepted by both of them.

References

1. *Kalpa Sūtra* (S.B.E. Vol. XXII) p. 286-87.
2. According to *Digambara* tradition Indrabhuti Gautam succeeded Mahāvira. It is quite strange as to why the *Svetāmbaras* tradition has ignored him as immediate successor of Mahāvira*
3. *Kalpa Sūtra* (S.B.E. Vol XXII) p. 287,
4. Roy, A, K, *A History of the Jains*, p, 90
5. Ibid. p. 93-95,
6. *Uttarddhyayan Sūtra* (SBE, Vol XLV) p, 123.